

On the Method of Moving Boundaries as Applied to the Measurement of the Absolute Velocity, and the Transport Number of Ions and of the Rate of Migration of Colloidal Particles.

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The theory of the moving boundary as put forth by Kohlrausch (Wied. Ann., 1897, 62, 209; see also Weber, Sitz. Kon. Preuss. Akad. Wiss., Berlin, 1897, 935) and the experiments of Masson (Phil. Trans., 1899, 192, 331), of Steele (Z. physikal. Chem., 1902, 40, 689) and of Dennison (Z. physikal. Chem., 1903, 44, 575; Trans. Farad. Soc., 1909, 5, 165) lead one to believe that a *stable boundary* can be realised when the slower moving ion follows the faster moving ion such that both move with equal speed. It has been repeatedly observed however that even in simple cases of two uni-univalent electrolytes having a common ion this condition is not sufficient (Steele, *loc. cit.*; Abegg and Gauss, Z. physikal. Chem., 1902, 40, 737; MacInnes and co-workers, J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1923, 45, 2246; 1924, 46, 1398; 1919, 41, 994, 1009; 1927, 49, 1710; see also H. S. Taylor, "Treatise on Physical Chemistry," Vol. I, pp. 547-49) and disturbing causes have been observed to operate which are not contemplated in this theory. A satisfactory explanation has so far not been obtained for these difficulties. It appears that apart from the case considered by Millar (Z. physikal. Chem., 1909, 69, 436) where the conditions on the two sides of the boundary are such that ions in one layer when they cross the boundary interact with ions in the other layer to form undissociated molecules and apart from the volume changes resulting from the concentration changes referred to by G. N. Lewis (J. Amer. Chem. Soc., 1910, 32, 862) the theoretical considerations underlying the theory on which these measurements are based have escaped a close scrutiny. MacInnes and co-workers remark (*loc. cit.*, 49 1715), "As explained in previous papers in this series, the ions of the leading solution and the indicator move at the same rate when the solutions are adjusted to the condition $C/T = C'/T'$... (1) *

* C, C' are the concentrations and T, T' the transport numbers respectively of the cations of the two electrolytes (with a common anion) which meet at the boundary.

which must be in general obtained by a series of experiments..... According to Kohlrausch and others the condition represented by Equation (1) should establish itself automatically, no limits of initial concentration being stated. However, we have found in general that this can only be relied on for deviation of 3 to 5 per cent. from the correct concentration. There are apparently additional influences, including diffusion that limit the range of adjustment." In their papers references to other difficulties will be found. Steele (*loc. cit.*) also refers to numerous difficulties specially regarding the production, maintenance and movement of a sharp boundary.

The method of moving boundaries is of greater importance for the measurement of cataphoretic velocity of colloidal particles as in contrast to the case of electrolytic ions this method constitutes at present the most suitable direct method available.

Kohlrausch's Theory of Moving Boundaries.

Let us consider the simplest case of a boundary between two univalent electrolytes AR and BR with a common anion R and further suppose that they are strong electrolytes in dilute solutions. Kohlrausch deduces the following relation regarding the rate of change of concentration of ions of one type with time in the interior of either of the electrolytes as the unidirectional current of constant strength i passes through the solution :—

$$\frac{\delta a}{\delta t} = - i \cdot f(a) \frac{\delta a}{\delta N} \quad \dots (2)$$

where δa is the change in concentration in the infinitesimal interval of time δt ; $\delta a/\delta N$ is the rate of change in concentration of the ion species under consideration obtaining during the interval δt along the direction N of the current and $f(a) = \delta n/\delta a$ where δn is the change in the transport number of the ion (a cation) when the concentration of the ion (or the electrolyte) changes by δa . In deducing this relation Kohlrausch assumes that the electrolytic neutrality in the interior of the solution is satisfied under all conditions, and he states: "*Freie Ionen Können daher unter keinern Umständen im Inneren von Lösungen entwickelt werden, sondern nur an metallisch leitenden Electroden*" (p. 214). This condition must be satisfied if Ohm's Law is to remain valid. It is not necessary to overlook the existence of

free ions of both signs freely moving in the solution. All that is necessary is that in a surface at right angles to the direction of the current, the condition of electrical neutrality should be satisfied. Kohlrausch next considers the possibility of the existence of excess ions of one sign at the boundary itself and concludes (p. 216): "Auch die Ionenmengen der Helmholtz'schen Doppelschichten, welche den Sprung des Potentials an der Berührungsstelle verschiedenartigen Electrolyte bewirken, sind, selbst wenn man Contact in Molecularabständen annimmt, so klein, dass sie zur Leitung nicht merklich beitragen.

Die "freien Ionen" werden hiernach die Stromvorgänge nicht in wahrnehmbarem Maasse beeinflussen."

It will be seen that Kohlrausch (from his calculations) consider that "free ions" (excess of ions of one sign) need not be taken into consideration. Kohlrausch next considers the case of a dilute solution of several electrolytes and deduces the following relation,

$$\frac{a}{a} + \frac{\beta}{b} + \dots + \frac{\rho}{r} + \dots = \text{a constant} \quad \dots (3)$$

which is independent of time; where a, β, \dots are the concentrations of the cations, ρ, \dots are the concentrations of the anions, a, b, \dots the mobilities (assumed to be constant) of the cations and r, \dots are the mobilities of the anions and remarks (p. 222), "Diese Summe möge beharrliche Function heissen." In fact this is the fundamental equation on which Kohlrausch bases his further treatment of the subject. Applying the above relation to the case of a mixture of several electrolytes with an ion of one sign in common, he obtains when the electrolyte is contained in a cylindrical tube with parallel layers of varying concentrations at right angles to the axis of the tube, the following relation:

$$\frac{a}{n} + \frac{\beta}{n_B} + \dots = \text{a constant, independent of time} \dots (4)$$

Equation (4) signifies that the sum of the ratios of the concentration to the transport number for all the ions when the mobilities are constant and independent of concentration remains unaffected by the passage of the current. In these discussions Kohlrausch so far assumes a continuous change in concentration from point to point. Taking the case of a boundary between two single electrolytes AR

and BR at any section normal to the direction of the current and in the interior of each electrolyte relationships

$$\frac{\alpha}{n_A} + \frac{\rho}{n_R} = \text{constant} \quad \dots \quad (5) \quad \frac{\beta}{n_B} + \frac{\rho}{n'_R} = \text{constant} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

must be independent of time. But it does not follow necessarily from Kohlrausch's treatment that this relationship will remain valid for the discontinuous transition at the boundary of the two electrolytes AR and BR. Kohlrausch recognises this and remarks (p. 235): "Es mögen noch einige Bemerkungen über den Fall folgen, dass verschiedene Lösungen mit scharfen Grenzen aneinander stossen, wobei der Unstetigkeit wegen die Folgerungen aus den Differentialgleichungen nicht ohne weiteres gelten."

Kohlrausch in effect considers the case of a sharp transition between two electrolytes as being a limiting case of continuous transition. He treats particularly the discontinuous transition between two different concentrations of a single electrolyte and of a dilute mixture of several electrolytes with a common ion. He points out that in these cases the relationship in Equation (3) remains valid. In connection with the case of a boundary that is, a discontinuous transition from concentration α_1 to concentration α_2 of a single electrolyte AR Kohlrausch remarks (p. 235): "Es treten von der einen Seite gerade soviele Ionen heran, wie auf der anderen Seite abgeführt werden." It is evident that the validity of Ohm's Law is assumed for the boundary and is considered to be a sufficient condition for the applicability of Equation (3) at the boundary for such sharp transitions. Regarding the case of a sharp transition between two electrolytes AR and BR, it appears that Kohlrausch does not definitely claim the validity of relation (3) but first considers that a sharp boundary exists and shows that the relation $\alpha/n_A = \beta/n_B$ must be satisfied. He remarks further (p. 238): "Man sieht, dass diese Betrachtung zu derselben Bedingung führt, wie die vorige: die oft genannte beharrliche Function muss zu beiden Seiten der Grenze denselben Werth haben." Kohlrausch concludes (p. 239): "Diese und ähnliche Fälle lassen sich, wenn man die Voraussetzung macht, dass die Lösungen sich mit scharfen Grenzen verdrängen, leicht construieren und die Resultate erscheinen als specielle Fälle von Folgerungen aus der Differential

Gleichungen. *Ob aber die wandernden Grenzen scharf bleiben, ist eine Frage, die durch besondere Betrachtungen über die Unstetigkeitsstellen entschieden werden muss. Nach einer mir ebenfalls von Heinrich Weber mitgetheilten Betrachtung ergeben sich auch andere Möglichkeiten.*"

Weber (*loc. cit.*) basing his considerations on these assumptions subjects these cases of non-uniform (sharp) transitions to a more rigorous mathematical treatment and obtains the general result that for the case of a *mixed solution* of two electrolytes AR and BR a non-uniformity at any cross section of the expression $\frac{a}{n_A} + \frac{\beta}{n_B}$ must remain at the same place during the passage of the current. Weber shows further that for a general solution based on the differential equations of Kohlrausch even in this simple case (p. 939) the movement of regions of discontinuities requires special treatment and concludes (p. 942): "Auf Grund der bisher gemachten Voraussetzungen lässt sich mathematisch nicht entscheiden, welche von aller diesen Lösungen dem wirklichen Verlauf am meisten entspricht. Physikalisch dürfte aber doch wohl der stetigen Lösung der Vorzug zu geben sein, zumal wenn man, wie es ja der Wirklichkeit entspricht, die Unstetigkeit nur als idealen Grenzfall eines sehr schnellen stetigen Überganges betrachtet." *On the above assumption of a discontinuous transition being a limiting case of continuous transition for the boundary between the two electrolytes AR and BR it is shown by Weber that when the slower moving ion follows the faster moving ion the concentrations on both sides of the boundary automatically adjust themselves to satisfy Equation (1) and the boundary remains stable.*

Let us consider the transfer of ions across these boundaries with a view to examine closely how far we are justified in treating discontinuous transitions as a limiting case of continuous transitions. Kohlrausch (see particularly p. 235, also Weber *loc. cit.* p. 940) refers to the transference of ions across the boundary normal to the axis of the cylinder on both sides of which there is a *sharp transition* of concentrations either of the *single electrolyte AR* or of the *mixed solutions of electrolytes AR and BR*. In the latter case Kohlrausch mentions that the *total number of the ions A and B taken together that enters the layer is equal to that which leaves it*. The case of the sharp boundary between two concentrations of the *same electro-*

lyte is simpler and the above statement holds good. This is an essential condition so that Ohm's Law might be applicable. And this condition remains true whether the transition is continuous or discontinuous so long as Equation (3) holds good.

We shall see in the next section that in contrast to the above instances this condition is not satisfied in the case of a boundary between AR and BR even when Equation (1) is satisfied, and it constitutes the main reason why such a discontinuous transition cannot be taken as the limiting case (*i.e.*, only differing in degree) of a continuous transition.

*The Validity of Ohms Law near the Boundary between two
Electrolytes AR and BR when the slower Moving Ion
follows the faster Moving Ion and Both move
at the same Speed.*

We shall now consider in detail the transference of the anion R across the boundary between AR and BR of concentrations C and C' respectively between which the relationship of equation (1) obtains. The condition that both ions would move at the same speed as also the condition that the differential equations of Kohlrausch are valid at the boundary require that the potential gradients in the layer on the two sides of the boundary and immediately contiguous to it must be inversely proportional to the mobility of the cation. As the slower moving ion is following the faster moving ion, for obvious reasons, there cannot be any mixing of the two cations. We should thus have a sharp boundary. The anion R is also simultaneously moving through the tube with the negative current and whereas B cannot overtake and cross the boundary to the layer of electrolyte AR or *vice versa*, the ions R are crossing the boundary at each instant under consideration. Now the actual speed of the ions R in the two layers are in the ratio of the potential gradients, that is, they are inversely proportional to the mobility of the cations in the layers (*cf.* Equation 1). Evidently the number of ions R coming from the layer of electrolyte AR (containing the faster moving cation A) into the layer of electrolyte BR immediately contiguous to the boundary will not be equal to the number of ions R coming from BR to AR, unless the concentrations of ions R in the two layers are inversely proportional to the potential gradient in each layer.

Referring to Figure 1 we find that the number of ions R crossing the

Figure 1.

boundary and entering into the immediately contiguous layer of electrolyte BR will be given by

$$i \cdot (n_R)^{AR} \cdot dt$$

where i denotes the *current density* and $(n_R)^{AR}$ is the transport number of the ion R in the electrolyte AR. We are assuming that during the interval dt the concentrations of AR and BR remain the same and the condition of electrical neutrality holds good on both sides of the boundary. These ions coming from the layer AR will spread into a thickness dx in the layer BR given by the relation:

$$dx = V'_R dt \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

where V'_R is the actual speed of the ions R in the layer BR and is given by $P_{BR} \cdot V_R$, where P_{BR} is the potential gradient in the layer BR and V_R is the mobility of the ion R per unit potential gradient,

The number of ions leaving the layer of BR of thickness dx contiguous to the boundary in the interval dt is given by $i \cdot (n_R)^{BR} \cdot dt$. Since $(n_R)^{BR}$ is greater than $(n_R)^{AR}$ the layer of volume dx contiguous to the boundary and containing the slower moving cation will be poorer (negative sign) in R by

$$-i \cdot \left\{ (n_R)^{BR} - (n_R)^{AR} \right\} dt \dots \dots \dots (8)$$

Substituting the value of dt in (7) we have:

$$-i \cdot \left\{ (n_R)^{BR} - (n_R)^{AR} \right\} \frac{dx}{P_{BR} \cdot V_R} \dots \dots \dots (9)$$

Evidently there will always be a *defect* in the number of anions in the layer of BR contiguous to the boundary unless the term within the bracket is equal to zero. The condition for an equality in the transport numbers is either—

(a) That the two cations must have the same mobility, or (b) that the mobility of the anion is so great compared to that of the cations that the transport number of the anion is the same in both cases.

Taking the value of i to be 5 milli-amperes (per sq. cm.) which is about one-tenth of the current density used by MacInnes and the boundary to be between hydrochloric acid and lithium chloride we find that the number given by Equation (9) is several times greater than the total number of ions in the volume dx , or in other words the volume dx would contain only positive charges and the electrical density will be enormous. On account of the free motion of the ions in the liquid it is evident that the consequent enormous value of the non-uniform potential gradient will oppose the separation of electricity, and in effect a drag will act on the ions preventing a separation of electricity. There is therefore no escape from the conclusion that the fundamental differential equations of Kohlrausch, based as they are on the assumption of electrical neutrality and the validity of Ohm's Law, are not applicable to the layer on the side of the boundary containing the electrolyte BR. The sharpness or diffused character of the boundary will be greatly affected by the relationships discussed above,

The condition in the layer of the electrolyte AR is, however, in contrast to that in the electrolyte BR and the ions A travel in a 'uniform ionic environment.' The ions R always pass by the ions A along the direction of the negative current at a rate governed by the conditions in the single electrolyte AR. The actual speed of the ions A (or R) in two layers of different concentrations of AR whether the transition is continuous or discontinuous will be directly proportional to the potential gradients which in any two layers of the same electrolyte must be inversely proportional to the concentrations of the electrolyte obtaining in them. It follows that the actual speed will be inversely proportional to the concentrations. The total number of the ions A (or R) leaving any layer will be proportional to the product of the concentration in the layer and the actual speed. Since the actual speeds of the ions are inversely proportional to the concentrations, the product of the actual speed and the concentration is constant for all layers and the number of ions entering or leaving any layer lying wholly within the electrolyte AR will therefore be constant and independent of the position of the layer. Thus at the boundary between AR and BR the ion A always moves through the electrolyte AR and as the ions R which pass them come from the single electrolyte AR, the ionic environment of the ions A remains unchanged with the passage of the current. The position is however different regarding the ions B and R. We thus see that the effect of the electrical separation discussed above would least influence the movement of A but would considerably influence the movement of B and R in a manner not contemplated by Kohlrausch.

These conclusions are in complete agreement with the observations recorded in the literature. We find that the boundary method is recognised not to give correctly the actual speed of the ions. As usually used the rate of motion of two boundaries are simultaneously observed and it is always the motion of the faster moving ion that is measured. Experimental arrangements are always such that the faster moving ions move into a single electrolyte consisting of these ions and having a constant concentration* although Steele (*loc. cit.*, pp. 699-700) lays down the following conditions in order that correct values of the transport numbers comparable to those obtained by the usual methods may be obtained:—

(1) The mobility of the indicator ion must be smaller than that of the ion whose transport number is being measured.

The liquid junction potential is thus non-existent inside the electrolyte.

(2) The indicator ion should not produce a precipitate with the solution under investigation.

(3) During the electrolysis no such ions must come into being which moves faster than the ion under measurement.

(4) The specifically lighter solution must be on the top of the heavier one.

(5) The resistance of the indicators should not be much greater than that of the solution which it follows.

(6) The potential gradients must lie within certain limits depending on the nature of the solutions which form the boundary.

It will be seen that conditions (5) is exactly what is implied in Equation (8). Steele considered that the observed difficulties originated from the heat developed on the passage of the current. While this is, no doubt, an important factor as has been emphasised by MacInnes it is clearly not a sufficient explanation in the numerous instances where the boundary remains sharp and perfectly horizontal. Some of these difficulties are summed up in condition (6) which along with condition (5) is not contemplated in the formulae of Kohlrausch and Weber. This has been pointed out by Steele who has investigated the conditions for a sharp boundary somewhat in detail. He attributes the difficulties in part to diffusion. From our experiments on cataphoresis it appears that convection currents on account of unequal changes in density destroy a sharp boundary. MacInnes considered this heating effect as also diffusion but finds that they are not sufficient to explain the want of adjustment postulated by Kohlrausch.

The effect of the unequal movement of the anions just considered would amount to a drag on the slower moving cation and the anion. It has been pointed out already that Kohlrausch considers that the quantities of free ions associated with liquid junction potentials are negligible so far as their effect on the conduction of electricity and on Ohm's Law is concerned. It would appear that this assumption is not justifiable for all liquid junctions specially during the conduction of electricity as we have seen above that the electric current tends to produce an excess of one of the ions. And thus increase the potential drop at the junction. From Equation (9) it seems reasonable to assume that the boundary will be sharp and will move at a steady rate when the potential gradients on the BR sides of the boundary have so adjusted themselves that the same number of chlorine ions leave and enter the layer of electrolyte BR contiguous

to the boundary and necessarily the condition for production and maintenance of such a boundary would depend on the potential gradients in the two layers and on the transport numbers of the ion R in the two electrolytes. It should be stated that we are not considering in detail the effects of diffusion and of the densities of the two layers and their variations on the passage of the current. As to the exact nature of the conditions at the boundary, several possibilities arise. It is intended to consider these in a separate investigation.

To sum up, it appears from the above considerations that in the homogeneous solution AR with two specifically lighter indicator solutions BR and AR' on its top as usually arranged in such experiments the ions A and R will be moving at the two boundaries

through a uniform ionic environment and if the potential gradient, or the current density and the concentration in the solution AR of constant strength be known their transport numbers can be determined: because though the drag at the boundary may have a disturbing effect its magnitude will be very small inside the electrolyte AR. But the adjustments at the boundary will not be governed by the equations of Kohlrausch and Equation (1) is not alone sufficient to characterise a satisfactory boundary. The current density and the transport numbers of the anion in the two layers are important factors. It also follows from Equation (9) that even in those cases where it is possible to determine the transport numbers by the boundary method, the movement of the boundary does not necessarily give the correct mobilities of both ions unless the transport number of the common ion has the same value in both electrolytes. The consideration of Kohlrausch and of Weber really do not postulate the difference between the two electrolytes AR and BR which underlies the conception of specifying the electrolyte with the slower moving ion as the 'indicator' solution. *One should from their theory expect the movement of the boundary to give correctly the mobilities of both ions.* It is well known to workers on this subjects that the boundary method is not at all suitable for this purpose. On the other hand it follows from the foregoing considerations in agreement with experience, that the usual method is suitable for the measurement of transport number of ions but not for the determination of absolute velocities.

The Boundary Method and Cataphoretic Measurements.

Equation (8) gives the conditions under which a determination of the absolute velocities of ions will be satisfactory. A discussion of these conditions is more important in the study of cataphoretic velocities of colloidal particles as in contrast to electrolytic ions the boundary method constitutes the most useful method available.

The methods based on the analogy of Hittorf's measurements of transport numbers are evidently unsatisfactory. From the equations of Kohlrausch as also from the preceding discussion it is not difficult to show that in colloids containing electric carriers (including electrolytic ions) of the same sign of different mobilities the conditions at different places of the colloidal solution cannot remain constant and the changes in concentration of the carriers of different categories that must result from the conduction of electricity will give us an average effect and not an absolute value of transport numbers. A physical interpretation of the data is not possible unless one knows the concentrations and mobilities of the carriers of electricity contained in the liquid. The exact interpretation will be very complicated. Even assuming that the concentration is uniform to begin with and that the products of electrolysis do not enter the colloidal solution changes in the relative concentrations of the charged particles are bound to occur on the passage of the current. This method rests on the integral effect of the current and it has been pointed out by Weber that it has not so far been possible to solve the integral effect in terms of the known factors, namely, the concentrations and mobilities of the different carriers. This method is only applicable in the case of simple colloids containing, say for example, carriers of any one sign having not more than one value for their mobility. Even then the values obtained by this method, being merely the integral changes in concentration on the passage of a current, requires a knowledge of the composition of the carriers for their interpretation in terms of the actual mobilities. An instance of the difficulties may be cited. For mixed solutions of the simple electrolytes AR and BR such that A and B have identical mobilities Kohlrausch shows that provided that to start with the concentrations of the ions are not constant all through the liquid, all that his differential equation implies is that the sum of the concentrations of A and B will remain unchanged on the passage of the current at any point but the ratio of their concen-

trations will change and Weber has shown that the integral effect admits of more than one solution, even if the direction of the current remains unchanged. There will be a change in the ratio of the concentrations of A to B and the transport numbers will appear to be different though we have started from the premise that the two have the same mobilities and, as they have a common ion, also the same transport numbers.

The moving boundary methods as usually used in cataphoretic measurements follow the procedure used by Burton (*Phil Mag.*, 1906, vi, 1, 425; compare also Galecki, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1912, 74, 174; Pauli, Hofmeisters Beitrage, *Z. phys. Chem. u. Path.* 1906, 7, 531; Michaelis, *Koll. Zeit.*, 1924, 34, 326; Powis, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 89, 91). Burton's procedure sometimes yields results which vary as much as 300%. As a result of an investigation into the sources of error the writer has developed a procedure (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, 103A, 102; see also Freundlich and Zeh, *Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1925, 114, 84; Kruyt and Willigen, *Zeit. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 130, 170; also *Koll. Zeit.*, 1928, 44, 82) which obviates the difficulties arising out of a failure to consider the boundary conditions. The improvement consists in finding out an electrolyte which does not disturb the initial uniform potential gradient in the liquid and in directly measuring the potential gradients in different layers before and after the passage of the current. Colloidal arsenious sulphide particles carry with them mobile hydrogen ions. The boundary can only be stable when the upper layer in the U-tube is a dilute solution or a strong acid with an anion which moves faster than the negatively charged colloidal particle. It was found, however, that no noticeable adjustment takes place at the boundary (*loc. cit.* pp. 118-119) and a substitution of hydrochloric acid by sulphuric acid having the same specific conductivity as the colloid did not alter the rate of migration to an extent greater than the limits of experimental error. It has also been observed that under these conditions, the same cataphoretic speed is obtained (within the limits of experimental error) whether the slower moving carriers follow the faster moving ones or *vice versa*, though under most suitable conditions, it is possible to get results reproducible within 1%.

Colloidal particles settle on account of the difference between their density and that of the dispersion means. It is necessary in these cases to observe the cataphoretic speeds with both

rising and descending boundaries, in order to eliminate the speed of settling.*

As the result of a large number of measurements in the past few years, it has been found desirable to secure what may be termed *an identical ionic environment*' (Chaudhury and Raichaudhuri, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 498) during the movement of the colloidal particle and irrespective of the direction of the current.

The conditions for securing such an ionic environment can be understood in the light of Equation (8). The measurement of the cataphoretic velocity is obviously analogous to the measurement of the absolute velocity of an ion. With colloidal solutions of arsenious sulphide containing hydrogen ions in the mobile sheet of the double layer on account of the high mobility of the hydrogen ion, the disturbing effect given by Equation (8) will be negligible and any strong acid of same specific conductivity as the colloidal solution will secure uniform ionic environment, and the same speed will be observed both for rising and descending boundaries. The difficulties with a rising boundary pointed out by MacInnes (*loc. cit.* 1927) and considered by him to be due to irregular heating effects of the current do not occur as condition (5) laid down by Steele is satisfied. The particles are moving in a uniform ionic environment which is not materially affected by the direction of the current and it is immaterial whether the faster moving ion follows the slower moving ion or *vice versa*. As the hydrogen ions are the only carriers of positive electricity and the colloidal particles are the only carriers of negative electricity possessing the same mobility this colloid presents little difficulties in securing an 'identical ionic environment.'

On the other hand colloids such as ferric hydroxide presents considerable obstacles and require a detailed study of the nature of the carriers of electricity in order to secure a uniform ionic environment. Simplifications of our procedure as used by Freundlich (*loc. cit.*) and Kruyt (*loc. cit.*) are possible when these conditions have been determined from a preliminary study which can easily be carried out by our method. The use of the ultrafiltrate as the upper liquid does not always offer a way out as it is not free from objections (V. Gazzi, *British Chemical Abstracts*, A., 1928, April, 359).

* It appears that the phenomenon which is commonly known as "barophoresis" is more complicated than is generally supposed to be.

Our observations with a ferric hydroxide sol which will be published shortly are of interest as illustrating what determines a uniform ionic environment. They show clearly that a dilute mixed solution of ferric and hydrogen chlorides of a definite composition is the most suitable for measurement of cataphoretic velocity. Chemical considerations point out that this should be so as the ferric hydroxide hydrosol which has been used in the above investigation contain free ferric and hydrogen ions.

It is generally implied in discussions on measurements of transport numbers by the moving boundary method that the slower moving ion adjusts its concentrations so as to secure a stable boundary such that both ions move with the same speed (compare Abegg and Gauss, *loc. cit.*; MacInnes, *loc. cit.*). In that event it is impossible to measure correctly the cataphoretic speed of colloidal particles by the usual methods used for this purpose, as it does not take into consideration any such adjustment. Even if we take note of such an adjustment it is not possible to utilise this for a colloid of the type of ferric hydroxide sol containing carriers of positive electricity having several mobilities.

From the foregoing we conclude that the theoretical basis of methods of measurement of cataphoretic speed must rest on securing a 'uniform ionic environment' during the movement of the colloidal particles.

In conclusion we would refer to the bearing of the foregoing discussion on the theories and measurements of liquid junction potentials, which we intend to discuss in future in the light of experiments in progress in this laboratory.

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